

Language teachers with ADHD: Perspectives on work

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Abstract

In Japan, much research has been conducted regarding the experiences of neurodiverse students in the language classroom with several teacher-researchers offering recommendations for how to make language classrooms more inclusive and equitable. It is prudent to examine neurodivergence in teachers in order to understand how it affects teaching practices and perspectives on learning because current research on the experiences of neurodiverse language teachers is scarce. This paper seeks to fill the lacuna in this area and provide workplaces with concrete practical suggestions for how to support their faculty with ADHD. The paper reports initial findings of an interview study conducted with nine non-Japanese tertiary level instructors selected from the original sample (Jones and Clark, 2024). The research concerns three research questions: 1) How do language teachers with ADHD describe their everyday work lives? 2) What kind of supports and obstacles do language teachers with ADHD encounter in the workplace? 3) How can teachers with ADHD be better supported in the

workplace? While the sample population is university teachers in Japan, findings are relevant to other settings. The findings will be of interest to administrators and educators who wish to create a working environment that is inclusive for neurodiverse teachers.

Keywords: interview, Japan, language teaching, neurodiversity, work

Introduction

Attention-Deficit/ Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a condition that is diagnosed frequently in children yet symptoms often persist into adulthood with an estimated prevalence of 7.2% (95% confidence interval: 6.7 to 7.8) (Thomas et al., 2015). However, some people are never formally diagnosed with mental health conditions due to a variety of factors including social stigma and privacy concerns (e.g., Gold et al., 2016; van Beljouw et al., 2010). The physiological aspect of the condition is unrelated to neurobiological factors such as intelligence but actually driven by dopamine hormone dysregulation (Barkley & Benton, 2022). Low dopamine production negatively affects executive function, resulting in decision making difficulties for affected individuals, including issues with inception, progression and execution stages of tasks. Conversely, abundant levels of dopamine can contribute to productive states. This condition contributes to a misunderstanding that people with ADHD have all-or-nothing states of task completion depending upon dopamine secretion or level of interest.

The popular literature on ADHD appears to be highly polarised: many books are either neuronormative and view the condition from a deficit perspective, even when sympathetic (e.g., Barkley & Benton, 2022). Descriptions of the condition align with the symptoms found in *The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (5th ed.; DSM–5; American Psychiatric Association, 2013). In contrast, there are examples of books promoting ADHD as a 'superpower'

(e.g., Archer, 2016; Hallowell & Ratey, 2021). That is, people living with the condition are subject to a 'doom and gloom' medical perspective or else unrealistic tales of outlying examples of other people with ADHD who have transcended the negatives associated with the condition. Both perspectives complicate self-image and may occur alongside a desire to fit into a world designed for neurotypical people (Chapman, 2023).

Research on ADHD adults and their work lives is scarce which suggests that over time individuals devise coping strategies to work effectively (Canela et al., 2017). Yet, it cannot be assumed that ADHD ceases being a complicating issue, thus research on how individuals navigate professional spaces will bring, at the very least, awareness. Awareness is a necessary prerequisite for successful accommodation in the workplace. If adjustments are made to organizational systems, productivity and workplace satisfaction will likely increase. To this end, this article seeks to add to the research on ADHD adults working in the field of tertiary education.

Nine tertiary-level educators were interviewed using the video conferencing platform, Zoom. Topics explored include the intricacies of working as an educator with ADHD, perceptions about institutional supports and barriers in their working environment and perspectives on changes needed to make universities more inclusive for ADHD faculty. Although this study was conducted in Japan, its findings may provide valuable insights applicable to university settings in other parts of the world.

Literature Review

ADHD and Repercussions at Work

Although ADHD is often associated with childhood, in adulthood, the pressure of increased cognitive demands and responsibilities required of successful execution of work may exacerbate ADHD symptoms for affected individuals. Inattention may be the most prominent trait, with many participants in Fuermaier et al. (2021) reporting difficulty in managing schedules,

completing tasks and meeting deadlines. Adamou et al. (2013) noted that low performance may negatively affect relationships with upper management and immediate colleagues. Feelings of inadequacy may lead to self doubt in one's ability to succeed and fuel an irrational focus on doing enough, and in some cases more than what is necessary, leading to emotional exhaustion and possibly burnout (Brattberg, 2006). Helgesson et al. (2023) found that ADHD among young adults was associated with higher rate of unemployment, however, pharmacological treatment of ADHD has been associated with lower risk of long-term unemployment (Li et al., 2022). While unemployment may not be immediately connected to professional work such as teaching, there is a risk related to the increased precarity in English language teaching (Walsh, 2019) and in higher education in particular (Courtois & O'Keefe, 2015; Molesworth et al., 2009).

Possible Benefits of ADHD at Work

While those with ADHD may have symptoms of executive dysfunction, there are ways to leverage potential weaknesses (Adamou et al., 2013). When dopamine levels are low, the neurodivergent brain seeks novelty. During this period, creativity is boosted as the individual searches for new ideas to provide a rush of dopamine (Abraham et al., 2006; Bertilsdotter Rosqvist et al., 2023; Boot et al., 2020; White & Shah, 2006). In addition, during this period, tasks are easily tackled, sometimes to the point that individuals enter into a period of hyperfocus, during which a tremendous amount of work can be completed in a short period of time (Ashinoff & Abu-Akel, 2021). Thus, people with ADHD may be able to become experts in their specific fields of interest (Baer, 2015). The ability to process different kinds of information across disciplines would make these people expert problem solvers and innovators (Finke, 1996; Zhang, 2002).

Disclosure

Because of the persistent internal struggles those with ADHD encounter, it may be difficult to disclose any perceived weaknesses to colleagues. Disabled people "can never be sure what the attitude of a new acquaintance will be, whether it will be rejective or accepting, until the contact

has been made" (Goffman 2022, 13-14). This may also be true of neurodivergent people, including those with ADHD, whose condition may not be immediately apparent, but where traits may clearly manifest in early interactions. Potential stigmatization can lead to self-consciousness in situations when dealing with others who may not share the same stigma. In fact, the nature of whether ADHD should be considered a disability may be considered a form of internalised ableism, with many living with the condition considering themselves to be less stigmatized than others, or having lower support needs than those with physical disabilities, or even other neurodivergent people (Sensoy & DiAngelo, 2017).

As an adult, grappling with the changing nature of the condition, both the positive and negative traits, can complicate disclosure in professional spaces, often due to the stigma involved. ADHD and other neurodevelopmental conditions do not preclude intellectual acuity and academic thinking, per se, and therefore there is a growing visible number of neurodivergent academics. In academic settings, which one would hope to be more thoughtful and enlightened, ableism can be readily observed, both external to the individual concerned (e.g., Andrews, 2020; Rummery, 2020) and internalised (Leigh & Brown, 2020) in the pertinent case of Dolan's (2023) defensive senior colleague with ADHD. Of course, not all disabled people have internalised ableism, nor are all abled people wilfully discriminatory toward disabled people. However, calling attention to the neuronormative and abled serves to obfuscate, undermine and minimise issues raised by the disability rights movement, in much the same way as calling attention to men's rights and use of #AllLivesMatter were used to undermine the #MeToo and #BlackLivesMatter movements (Clapp, 2022; Grabowska & Rawluszko, 2020). Thus, in this article, while we make points that draw attention to positive experiences and advantages that ADHD teachers bring to the workplace, we do not trivialize the struggles that ADHD teachers face. Instead we seek to draw attention beyond the 'deficit' and 'disorder' associated with the condition.

Disclosure is not always desired, nor welcomed, and this may be true of ADHD people to other ADHD people, as well as the case of ADHD people to neurotypical people. An example of the disclosure causing discomfort in interactions between ADHD people can be seen in Dolan (2023), mentioned above. Other examples of ND disclosure causing problems are detailed in Fox and Gasper (2020), who state that disclosure of mental ill-health can be a risk to “career, employment and standing” (2020: 16). Arguably, such risks emerge from stigma, which may cause shame among stigmatised people because they witness traits in others that they themselves exhibit (Goffman, 2022). Disclosure to abled society also entails the risks of being patronised and pitied, consciously or otherwise. Furthermore, there is also a risk of receiving trivial concessions that make little if any difference to one’s quality of life, but which serve as performative acts of allyship (Kutlaca & Radke, 2023). Of course, disclosure need not always be negative, but it is always fraught with the potential of being further stigmatised and ultimately marginalised by the communities in which one participates and interacts. As such, the decision to disclose rests with individuals. More examples of the benefits and risks of disclosure are necessary in both research and popular literature.

Neurodiverse Teachers

While much attention has been paid to supporting students, there have been very few studies exploring the experiences of neurodiverse teachers in the English language teaching profession. Exploration of this area is essential because students frequently look to their teachers as role-models. For the neurodiverse student, having a publically neurodiverse teacher who is ‘like you’ would have a great impact on self-image (Rask & Bailey, 2002; Muir et al., 2021). Accordingly, research on neurodiverse instructors is important to understand how neurodiversity affects the dynamics between language teaching and learning. Examples include Sarchet’s (2020) call for institutions to cultivate cultures of self-advocacy so that all teachers, whether neurodiverse or not, participate fully in the educational environment. Additionally, Cuervo Rodriguez and Castañeda-Trujillo (2021) conducted a narrative inquiry of two dyslexic

pre-service English language teachers in Colombia. Furthermore, Wood et al. (2022) is an entire volume dedicated to the experiences of autistic teachers and how to build inclusive schools. Yet another is the special issue of *Fremdsprachen Lehren und Lernen* dedicated to a largely German language exploration of neurodiversity in foreign language teaching and teacher development, featuring voices from the neurodivergent community themselves (Bündgens-Kosten & Blume 2024). These examples show that research on/within neurodiverse and/or neurodivergent communities is entirely possible, and in particular show that such research need not employ a deficit-based perspective.

Japan-centred studies on neurodiversity among teachers includes the duoethnographic study conducted by Jones and Noble (2023) who examined the experiences of two middle-aged white male teachers who live with ADHD and work in Japan and Thailand. Taylor (2024)'s research with language teachers who battle chronic illness, presumably similar to conditions affecting cognitive processes like ADHD, offers a glimpse into how these teachers craft their work lives. With a considerable skew in their sample toward Japan-based participants, Jones and Clark (2024; also Clark & Jones, under review) examined the experiences of language teachers with ADHD in the workplace using a questionnaire survey. The results of the survey provided broad, thin-slice data, regarding the relative rewards and struggles of English language teaching.

Purpose of the Project

The purpose of this project is to provide important information for university administrations seeking to better support neurodiverse teachers, especially those who have ADHD. However, at least as importantly, we seek to share the experiences of language teachers with ADHD, in order to provide a platform for voices less frequently heard, and also to ensure that the ADHD voice is provided through an in-group perspective rather than an outside observer's ventriloquism, where researchers express their own points of view, and where research is 'done to' the community rather than 'done with' them (Oliver, 1992; Zinn, 1979).

Language teachers' experiences of their work lives can provide insight into the ways in which ADHD affects behaviors, decision-making and affect at work. Additionally, the supports and obstacles encountered in the workplace may also contribute to the preference or orientation toward certain tasks and the cognitive load associated with them. Moreover, ADHD language teachers' perspectives on what can aid them in the workplace are necessary because findings from general workplace studies on ADHD can lack the specificity required to inform decisions on localised policy and accommodations. The higher education context itself is diverse, and also divergent from other educational and workplace contexts within Japan. As such, it is useful to investigate the teachers' ideas based upon their experience, and then see how it aligns with findings from generalised contexts.

Research questions:

- 1) How do language teachers with ADHD describe their everyday work lives?
- 2) What kind of supports and obstacles do language teachers with ADHD encounter in the workplace?
- 3) How can teachers with ADHD be better supported in the workplace?

Materials and Methods

Participants

Participants from Jones and Clark (2024) were selected based on shared criteria: that they were non-Japanese, teaching in higher education, and either had a diagnosis of ADHD or self-diagnosis. Of those available for interview, the following agreed to participate (Table 1). Seven of the nine interview participants were female, and two male. Six of the participants' countries of nationality were in North America, two in Australasia, and one in Southeast Asia. One was in their 20s, three in their 30s, two in their 40s, and three in their 50s. All participants have been involved in language teaching for over five years.

Table 1: Interview participants

Pseudonym	Gender	Age	Nationality	Diagnosis
Christie	Female	50s	North America	Suspect
Wendy	Female	30s	North America	Yes
Barbara	Female	50s	Australasia	Yes
Olivia	Female	50s	North America	Suspect
Peter	Male	30s	Australasia	Yes
Kimberly	Female	30s	Southeast Asia	Suspect
Kenneth	Male	40s	North America	Suspect
Winona	Female	40s	North America	Yes
Tara	Female	20s	North America	Suspect

Privacy Measures and Data Collection

Semi-structured interviews were conducted in English using videoconferencing software. A list of questions is provided in the Appendix. The length of interviews ranged from 30 minutes to 120 minutes. Video files were stored on the researchers' password protected computers. Participants were informed that their anonymity would be protected through the use of pseudonyms and the redacting or alteration of any identifying information and they signed declarations of informed consent to use their data in this research.

Data Processing and Analysis

The first author used Word365 dictation speech-to-text function for the initial transcription of five interviews. The second author transcribed four interviews manually. After initial transcription, both authors proofread their own transcripts for accuracy and then conducted phenomenological analysis, with contextual themes chosen and expressed according to participants' perspectives (Brinkmann, 2013). Once the article was finished, it was sent to all nine participants to allow them to confirm our interpretation of any text concerning them as part of the data triangulation process of member checking (Richards, 2015).

Results

RQ1: How do language teachers with ADHD describe their everyday work lives?

An Ideal Day

Our participants had a strong image of how a work day should unfold. For example, Winona took pride in being prepared for a lesson in advance. Barbara commented that having continuous wifi access and prepared slide decks would ensure her day went well. Kenneth remarked that a smooth workday was one in which he could "tick all of the boxes" on his lesson plan and finish his work in a timely manner if not early. Yet, for him external stimuli such as inclement weather and train delays caused difficulties because he needed to adjust his lesson plan. Peter remarked that an email inbox full of messages from colleagues was enough to break his focus when teaching. Similarly, for others, forgetting to bring teaching materials or procrastinating on work-related tasks disrupted a work day.

The Ideal Teacher

The participants felt a keen sense of what teaching is and how teachers should behave. When speaking of her colleagues and her tendency to avoid them, Kimberly said:

I don't talk a lot to them because I think the more I talk the more I find out that there are things that they do so I just don't really... it makes me wanna not... it makes me feel like I

have less faith in them, less confident in them if I ever needed to, you know use their lesson plans or something like that, I don't feel like I could because they're not being very careful about this whole planning. [Kimberly].

Christie spoke of some part-time colleagues in the early days of her career as "raking in the cash and [they're] putting as little as possible out, like [they're] completely cynical about the students". Retrospectively, she perceives her past self as different and actively striving to make a meaningful impact on her students' lives. Now, she acknowledges that, while she was kind in the past, she does not consider herself an especially effective teacher at that time.

Engagement with Work Tasks

Engagement with work depends on the type of task. Three participants (Christie, Olivia, Tara) said that there is a potential for things to be boring so they use a variety of activities to keep lessons interesting for them but also for their students. Repetitive tasks such as pronunciation drills or marking student papers were mentioned as something that is explicitly boring by Olivia. During marking, it is easy for her to overlook errors in student writing, but when she is checking work alongside her students at the language centre at her university, she finds it easier to concentrate and focus on minute details.

Strategies and Systems

Some of the participants expressed an orientation toward systems-based working. For example, Barbara mentioned that she was adept at designing systems to organise her work. Kenneth explained that one reason that he moved into a leadership role in which he coordinates other teachers is that

I knew that if I could do that job I could not only kind of help mitigate, fix those own factors within myself but then I could also learn how those problems, uh, arose and how to deal with them.

On the one hand, adopting new self-designed systems may not always be efficient; as Barbara stated, it can be like “building a better mousetrap”, i.e., working in elaborate ways that are no better than simpler alternatives. On the other hand, it must be noted that neurotypicals can also be inefficient, and perhaps even less efficient than neurodivergent people. Therefore redesigning systems can empower people who feel weakened by existing systems that do not work for them.

Thoroughness

The participants also described the lengthy effort they put into preparing teaching materials or marking student work. Winona described her system for assessing presentations:

I make myself, for presentations, a chart and then I kind of like make notes in the chart and then I can kind of compare all the groups and then kind of give a good score range based on that... so for presentations *I always record them and I rewatch them* because during the presentation I can't focus enough on the presentation and what's going on in class and the paper in front of me... [Winona, italicized for emphasis].

The many facets of what goes into an effective presentation seem to overwhelm her and extend the time it takes to assess. Similarly, Kimberly described her dedication to improving her materials every semester. When asked if she prepared more than her colleagues, she said,

Definitely. 1000%. Everything, down to the fonts to the color of the PowerPoint to the content, I change every semester. I relook at all my stuff, even though I'm teaching the same courses... I'm still just trying to make everything better, like even with old courses. New classes, oh my gosh *the planning doesn't ever end* (italicized for emphasis).

Peter spoke of his affinity for the work by saying

I find it very easy to hyperfixate on teaching so I guess maybe then if anything, it's a positive effect because none of the teaching aspects I get muddled on. So when I'm prepping, even right through grading, I find it very easy to focus on that.

These excerpts illustrate that for these three participants the work seems to be pleasant and/or creative. Winona has created a rubric to enable her to provide more effective feedback to her students, Kimberly is focusing on details regarding planning, including relatively minor details. Furthermore, Peter has stated that preparation and teaching are easy to hyperfocus on without confusion, and therefore it may be assumed that these all are pleasant experiences.

Relationships

Workplace relationships are easier to navigate for some participants than for others. Winona finds the office politics of her tenured position stressful. When she talks about colleagues, her comments are negative in general, however, when she talks about her students, she mentions that the relational aspects are rewarding. In contrast, Barbara rarely mentions colleagues, possibly because she is a part-time employee at her universities, but she explicitly mentions the rewards of relationships with her students. Barbara spoke of the joy she feels

as long as I see them, as long as I see them talking and smiling and laughing during a class, then that's a good day. And if I have at least one kid going 'Ah!', that is a really good day.

Olivia also prioritized students and their learning in her work as a language advisor. She said, "I help them improve their language learning strategies, so if they found some breakthrough in that where they've realised a better way for themselves to learn, then that's really satisfying for both of us."

Teaching is an inherently social profession, requiring interaction with students, colleagues, other professional staff and stakeholders. This social nature of the profession may create difficulties for some neurodivergent teachers, for various reasons. For Tara, social cues can be difficult to perceive: “sometimes when I’m in general conversation more like this [interview] I will actually miss signals that somebody is getting sick of my monologuing.” Furthermore, some participants noted that they had poor relationships with their colleagues, due to either speaking their mind (Christie) and/or perceiving slights against them by colleagues (Winona).

RQ2: What kind of supports and obstacles do language teachers with ADHD encounter in the workplace?

Support 1: Collegial Atmosphere

None of the participants mentioned asking for formal accommodations at work. Yet, some negotiated accommodations with immediate supervisors and all constructed various coping strategies to succeed with work tasks. For example, both Barbara and Olivia explained their supervisors were open to hearing their opinions and concerns. Barbara feels she can ask her administration for any kind of classroom or equipment and it will be arranged because they see her helping the “difficult” students succeed. Olivia spoke highly of her supervisor and the support she gives. Tara explained she feels very supported because she can ask questions of her colleagues in a text messaging group.

Support 2: Flexibility

In addition to direct support, the participants identified other institutional systemic characteristics that are helpful. For example, several participants noted flexibility is key. For Wendy, having a free period at the beginning of the day acts as a “buffer” for her to mentally prepare for the work day ahead. While this schedule was not created specifically to accommodate her needs, she appreciates days like this. Similarly, Christie is a tenured professor with her own office. She

emphasized that having a private space to decompress that is organized to her liking was important for her to recover from a busy teaching day.

Support 3: Autonomy

A lot of the participants mentioned autonomy as something that helps them to work optimally. A pertinent example is from Wendy, whose supervisor is very “hands-off”. She explains that while parameters are set, “I have, like, so much freedom in how I [teach] that I'm not constrained, I don't feel like I'm fighting my own brain when I'm in the class.” Additionally, Olivia explained

we have guidelines...these are our goals but achieve them how you like. So that's nice. I can do what I want .. I couldn't imagine being at a school where you're told what to do and how to do it. That would be a nightmare for me. I like to do things my way.

Conversely, Kenneth thrives in his regimented environment where he is able to “cross pollinate” and use the same activity in different skills classes because he “[knows] the general linear layout of what's happening in all of those classes from start to finish, from beginning to end of their timelines.”

Obstacles

Obstacle 1: Ableism

The participants frequently compared their personality or actions with those of their peers, aside from Peter, who felt that in academia “all of us are weird so it doesn't matter”. There were some differences among the other participants that manifested in the beliefs and experiences of ADHD disclosure, with a spectrum of extreme openness at one end and negative experience of disclosure at the other. Peter is open about his neurodiversity, for the reason stated above. Additionally, Wendy stated a belief that she could consult her supervisor about any accommodations that she may require related to her ADHD. However, there were more detailed negative expectations or outcomes related to disclosure. Both Kimberly and Winona were

fearful of disclosing their neurodivergency to colleagues. Kimberly stated strong beliefs related to colleagues and the atmosphere at work that being public about her neurodivergency would be almost another strike against her:

The thing is like ADHD is kind of like a buzzword these days and it's almost like a cliché and there are people who view it as like it's an excuse. You're going to use it as an excuse for you when you fail to do something or when you are unable to do something. I feel like there are people who would view it that way and I think as a person who's you know a woman of color and just... there are already so many things against me. I don't feel comfortable sharing things with them that would just make them think of me as an attention seeker of sorts. [Kimberly].

That is, the stigma is generally external, but the size of the stigma is related to projections of social acceptance or rejection. However, the stigma associated with ADHD, and arguably other neurodivergent conditions, operate within intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1991), and that being a minoritized person can amplify stigma and associated notions and stereotypes.

At the most negative end of the spectrum, when asked about whether she had disclosed her ADHD to colleagues, Winona's answer highlighted a situation that many people with invisible disabilities worry about: disclosure to her boss with the outcome that he "basically used that against me later and he's been like talking down to me for like years." This situation is also compounded by a newer Japanese colleague having

made a lot of passive aggressive comments about like my office being messy or about foreign teachers being entertaining but like kind of implied like oh like (falling intonation) 'Oh well, the students love you because you're entertaining and you're being like fluffy and not (rising intonation) fake kind of a thing.'

The notion implied by the comments from Winona's colleague insinuate that any success is only due to difference, and is not actually due to expertise. Thus, the nature of ADHD symptoms can make teaching professionals appear to be less professional than they actually are, at least in the eyes of some colleagues.

Obstacle 2: Institutional Norms

Lack of clarity regarding institutional practices was challenging for some participants. Olivia works in isolation in a learning center and admitted she didn't know basic things about the school such as the time schedule. Similarly, because she does not attend regular staff meetings, Tara feels that her parameters of work and who to consult when an issue arises is unclear. She explains

it's sometimes challenging to know what expectations are and I personally have found that not having other people around doing similar duties to kind of keep on pace with makes it hard to know like when I'm hyperfixating on something that I need to break away from. (Tara)

Similarly, Kenneth suggests that camaraderie with colleagues is important for him and "people would benefit from the periodic ability to hear other people's voices and to compare their own cacophony and chaos to those of others." This contrasts sharply with the ambivalence Kimberly has toward her colleagues and that Christie felt toward her previous part-time colleagues.

Obstacle 3: Issues with the Physical Environment

Participants mentioned several issues with their teaching environment that disrupted their work. These ranged from simple annoyances such as dry whiteboard markers (Christie) and tangled audio visual equipment cords left in disarray by previous faculty (Kimberly). Wendy complained about her busy staff room. Tara mentioned a two-factor authentication system to use the institutional wifi that frequently caused problems because it requires her to remember to bring her mobile phone with a full charge to class. Likewise, audiovisual hubs requiring a key stored in a separate administration building posed additional challenges for her.

Obstacle 4: Heavily Coordinated Curriculums

Three participants explained that using pre-made materials is problematic for them and that latitude to plan lessons in their own way is essential. For both Wendy and Kimberly the process of making slides is a necessary step in lesson planning. Wendy explains

I am useless if I try to grab someone else's PowerPoint for the most part...I flounder, cos I haven't processed them, [but] if there's a mistake in my slides, I can own up to that... But when someone else does it, it makes me so irrationally angry, like 'What idiot made these slides? Who did this?'

Similarly, Kimberly describes her planning/teaching in this way:

It has to be your own and you have to put your own element of stuff in it. No matter how many lesson plans we share, you're gonna put your own flair to the lesson so I would like to have something that is my own entirely that I don't have to explain to people all these little quirks that I have included in the lesson plans. [Kimberly]

A further example was provided by Peter, who related a story about starting a new position at a new university and how he dealt with being tasked with using a textbook selected by the previous teacher. To solve this problem, he made the book itself the focus of learning and had

his pre-service teachers engage with it by analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of the textbook.

RQ3: How can teachers with ADHD be better supported in the workplace?

Clarify Institutional Norms

There were two main recommendations suggested by the participants. First, clear institutional expectations in tandem with a supportive faculty community is essential. The participants struggled with vague work parameters. Tara explained what it feels like at her workplace: “it's like a blind person trying to find like where the walls are and they're all made out of bubbles you know. If you touch it, it's like ‘Oh well it doesn't have to exist’”.

Wendy appreciates the freedom she has but at the same time feels specific work requirements might also help her. Winona feels her institution's culture is one in which “people just expect you to figure [norms] out by yourself” but “if you feel like you're bothering people all the time, it's very hard to actually be productive”. To this end, building a positive collegial community with open communication would be important for her. She feels dependent on her coworkers for institutional knowledge but at the same time is hesitant to ask for help. She suggests: “I think if there were more open communication and more working things out together, rather than everybody doing everything by themselves and very *nan demo ii* [anything goes], I think that would be very helpful.”

Normalize Neurodiversity

Moreover, the participants called for more awareness raising about neurodiversity, and an effort to normalize being different amongst not only students but within faculty relationships. Kimberly suggested

I think the university cannot support students who have ADHD even. So one of the best things that they could do perhaps is to have workshops. We need awareness raising workshops because there are very few teachers I believe who are trained especially in special education needs.

Additionally, Olivia made a plea for the students themselves,

I wish that people could be accepting. I wish that people could be supportive. I wish that they had ways to help children from when they're young. Understand that it's not them, that they are so good at so many things. It's just that they are fish being asked to fly and they're not good at that, and that's what's being tested and it breaks my heart to see it.

[Olivia]

However, while there is a naivety regarding ADHD and how it affects students, there may be more negativity toward colleagues. Tara's perspective was:

the cultural attitudes are very forgiving towards students but they're not forgiving towards adults and everybody just sort of expects that ...it disappears when you're an adult ...You learn how to cope with it and you do the best you can to get around it but like like you're trying to "hammer the nail... but I'm not a nail, I'm a screw! You can hit me all you want with the hammer. It ain't going to go down". [Tara]

Thus while students are expected to deviate from certain educational sociocultural norms, teachers may not have the option of deviation without detriment to themselves regarding the judgment of their colleagues.

Conclusion

The results show that nine participants in this interview study are extremely committed to their work as language teachers. They often devote large amounts of time to lesson preparation, teaching, and marking student work, which is likely due to the ADHD propensity to hyperfocus (Ashinoff & Abu-Akel, 2021). They all have a strong sense of how a teaching day should unfold and are cognizant of outside factors that may disrupt their flow. Relationships with students tend to be easy to navigate for them, but relationships with colleagues and supervisors vary (Fuermaier et al., 2021). As far as supports, the participants appreciate guidelines but prefer to accomplish specific tasks with individualized approaches, deriving satisfaction from being able to make a personal contribution to their work. Clear lines of communication between colleagues and supervisors strengthens the work they do and helps them to feel supported.

Problems in the workplace for most participants may be caused by a lack of understanding of institutional norms and inability to confirm expectations. While these problems may also manifest for neurotypical teachers, for ADHD teachers, this may cause stress, which could induce anxiety and defensiveness regarding making further mistakes or drawing attention to their shortcomings (Brattberg, 2006; Dolan, 2023; Goffman, 2022). Overly complicated or stringent systems that quash individualism and freedom are also problematic.

Finally, recommendations for improvements are twofold: The participants thrive in supportive collegial environments in which task expectations are clear. Yet, the participants also noted weaknesses concerning the situated knowledge within their institutions regarding neurodiversity and called for increased accommodation across all aspects of the academic sphere regarding neurodiversity for all, not only students but also instructors. However, some participants, particularly Winona, were troubled by disclosure, with the feeling that their ADHD status would be used against them, or actually was by supervisors. This resultant stigma is the result of a lack of understanding and awareness of ADHD as a neurodivergent condition, and also a lack of understanding and awareness of the specific skills, and enthusiasm that teachers bring to their work (Fox & Gasper, 2020; Goffman, 2022).

In conclusion, the participants thrive in the workplace yet also face considerable challenges regarding potential perceived shortcomings. Dolmage (2017) discusses the notion of student accommodations in academia as being a way to “make the disability go away. The aspiration here is not to empower students to achieve with disability, but to achieve around disability or against it, or in spite of it” (p. 70). However, as noted by Winona, while students are accommodated to an extent, teaching staff are expected to simply deal with difficulties. Certainly, the participants in this study have coping strategies (some similar to those detailed in Canela et al., 2017) to deal with workplace demands. Yet in spite of some of the rigidity of the higher education workplace, there are potential avenues to improve the workplace environment for teachers. We therefore call on higher education institutions to make explicit the support available to staff members, including teaching staff, and to avail themselves of the nascent literature developing around ADHD and wider neurodiversity.

Limitations

One aspect of the study for which we anticipate criticism is the wide variation in interview times, i.e., between 30 minutes and 90 minutes. However, we see such variance as essential; some of our participants explicitly valued the opportunity to share their experiences of being neurodivergent language teachers in detail to avoid ambiguity, while negotiating schedules between the researchers and participants for videoconferencing meetings necessitated some short meetings.

Furthermore, as with most qualitative interview studies, the sample size is small. This means that findings may not necessarily be generalised across contexts, but instead it is hoped that aspects of our findings and the solutions proposed resonate in other settings. That is, our small sample size actually affords in-depth, thick-slice analysis of the issues faced by language teachers with ADHD.

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Appendix

Interview questions

- 1) On the questionnaire, no one really mentioned language teaching in the responses at all. What drew you to language teaching as a profession?

- 2) If you remember our survey, we asked you to decide if having ADHD benefits or hinders work tasks like planning, teaching, marking etc. However, 25% of people flat out reported that it was difficult to discriminate. Do you find this as well? Could you give specific examples or describe a situation in which this dichotomy might surface?
- 3) Describe a good ADHD day and a bad day in your work life.
- 4) In the short answer sections of the survey, some people mentioned workplace characteristics that helped them do their job successfully. What are the best aspects of your workplace from the point of view of someone with ADHD?
 - a) support offices
 - b) university or departmental work systems
 - c) communication systems
 - d) technology/ teaching tools provided
 - e) classroom/ building infrastructure
 - f) anything else
- 5) What aspects of your workplace make work difficult for you as a teacher with ADHD?
- 6) How can your workplace/ employer/ colleagues support you better?
- 7) Finally, we are asking all of our interview participants to reflect on their decision to move to Japan. Do you think your ADHD affected your decision to move abroad?
- 8) Did/ does having ADHD affect your decision to take up language teaching and continue in the profession?